

Phenyl-Tin Cleavage by Some Ferrocenyl Hydrazones

S. R. PATIL, U. N. KANTAK and D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Pune-411 008

Ferrocenyl hydrazones of the type $\text{FcCH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{Ar}$ [where $\text{Fc}=\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Fe}$

C_5H_5 ; $\text{Ar}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (I), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ (II), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2$ (III), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$ (IV) and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (V)] form stable tin derivatives when reacted with triphenyltin acetate in benzene solution. Compound (I) gives hexacoordinated, octahedral tin(IV) complex, compound (II) gives penta-coordinated, trigonal bipyramidal tin(IV) complex, while compounds (III-V) give acetoxy bridged tin(IV) complexes which are dimeric in nature in solid form and monomeric in nature in chloroform solution. Evidences for their coordinated structures have been obtained from ir, pmr spectra and elemental analysis.

NELSON and Martin¹ have studied the interaction of chelating agents such as β -diketones, salicylaldehyde, 8-hydroxyquinoline with several organotin(IV) derivatives like tetraphenyltin, diphenyltin(IV) dichloride, triphenyltin chloride. They found that phenyl-tin cleavage is favoured at elevated temperatures, provided the ligand is present in high concentration. Such type of reactions can provide a convenient route for the preparation of new and interesting chelated tin compounds. Literature survey revealed no report on the interaction of chelating agents with triphenyltin acetate. In continuation of our studies on ferrocenyl hydrazones² we have investigated the reactions of some ferrocenyl hydrazones, $\text{FcCH}=\text{N}-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{Ar}$ [$\text{Fc}=\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{FeC}_5\text{H}_5$; $\text{Ar}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (I), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ (II), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2$ (III), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OH}$ (IV) and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (V)].

Materials and Methods :

Ferrocenyl hydrazones were prepared by the procedure reported elsewhere². Triphenyltin acetate was purchased from Aldrich Chemicals and used without further purification. All solvents were distilled and dried by standard procedures.

Preparation of tin(IV) complexes :

All the tin(IV) complexes were prepared by the following general procedure :

Triphenyltin acetate and ferrocenyl ligand in equimolar ratio were taken in benzene and the solution refluxed for about 8 hr. The hot mixture was filtered to remove insoluble impurities and the filtrate was concentrated under vacuum at 50°. The solid product thus obtained in almost quantitative yield was recrystallized from either benzene or chloroform and dried under vacuum. The compounds prepared along with their melting points and elemental analyses are given in Table 1.

Spectroscopic methods :

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 283B spectrophotometer using caesium iodide optics. PMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Associates Model T-60 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard.

Results and Discussion

Ferrocenyl hydrazones react with triphenyltin acetate in benzene at reflux temperature giving different kinds of tin derivatives. These tin deriva-

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES OF PHENYL TIN(IV) COMPLEXES OF SOME FERROCENYL HYDRAZONES

Sl. No.	Compound	Composition	Yield %	m. p. °C	Analysis %		
					C	H	N
1.	VI	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{Sn}$	95	252	60.39 (61.67)*	4.69 (4.31)	6.12 (5.99)
2.	VII	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{38}\text{N}_2\text{OClFeSn}$	85	255	61.39 (60.50)	4.96 (4.60)	4.40 (4.00)
3.	VIII	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{FeSn}$	90	235	54.48 (54.30)	4.10 (3.85)	6.18 (5.94)
4.	IX	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{FeSn}$	78	214	58.19 (58.65)	4.76 (4.16)	3.91 (4.13)
5.	X	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{FeSn}$	80	232	57.56 (56.69)	4.47 (4.24)	6.11 (6.32)

* Figures with parentheses are Calculated values.

* NCL Communication No. 2929.

tives are stable and soluble in common organic solvents.

The elemental analyses of these compounds clearly show that reaction of ferrocenyl hydrazone compound I and triphenyltin acetate gives tin(IV) complex of the formula $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(L_2)$ (VI), (where L=ferrocenyl hydrazone anion). In this case both the phenyltin cleavage and elimination of acetoxy group have been observed. However, interaction of compound (II) with triphenyltin acetate is found to result in the elimination of acetoxy group only giving tin(IV) complex of the formula $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(L)$ (VII). Yet, interaction of compounds (III-V) is found to proceed in a different manner giving novel acetoxy bridged tin(IV) complexes of the formula $[(C_6H_5)_2SnL(OAc)]_2$ (VIII-X).

The infrared spectra of the ligands in Nujol² show strong N-H and C=O (amide I) stretching vibration bands around 3220 and 1650 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\nu(N-N)$ band is found as a medium intense band around 920 cm^{-1} . The spectra of chelated tin(IV) complexes (Table 2) show the absence of absorption bands due to $\nu(N-H)$ and $\nu(C=O)$. Instead, two new bands are observed around 1605 and 1230 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the stretching vibrational modes of conjugate $>C=N-N=C<$ and C-O groups^{3,4}. A strong intense band around 1075 cm^{-1} can be assigned to phenyltin vibration⁵. This observation suggests that ligands enolize in solution and then bond with metal ions through replacement of amide proton. In the spectra of all the metal complexes amide-II band is shifted to lower frequency by about 30 cm^{-1} while $\nu(N-N)$ band is shifted to a slightly higher frequency by ca. 15 cm^{-1} . The negative shift in amide-II and the positive shift in $\nu(N-N)$ bands support the coordination through azomethine nitrogen atom. The characteristic bands of ferrocenyl moiety are observed as expected in the spectra. In the case of tin(IV) complex derived from compound

IV, broad and weak bands centered around 2930 cm^{-1} attributable to the intramolecular -OH bonding are expected to be observed, but identification of these bands is not possible due to the presence of ligand vibrations in this region.

The spectra in the region 1600-1450 cm^{-1} are complex for all these compounds due to overlapping of several absorption bands. Although acetoxy group frequencies are difficult to locate due to the complex pattern of the spectra, the presence of acetoxy group in compounds VIII-X has been indicated by elemental analysis and supported by pmr spectral data.

The metal-ligand vibrational modes are generally found to occur in the far infrared region between 600-200 cm^{-1} . However, in the spectra of these complexes it is not easy to locate metal ligand vibrations because of the various skeletal vibrations of the ligands. In this study, the assignments made (Table 2) are purely tentative and based mainly on the information available in literature. The strong bands around 495 cm^{-1} can be assigned⁶ to $\nu(Sn-O)$. The bands in the range 380-335 cm^{-1} and 610-600 cm^{-1} can be assigned to $\nu(Sn-N)$ and $\nu(Sn-C)$, respectively⁷⁻⁹.

The pmr spectral data of tin(IV) complexes (Table 3) show the presence of acetoxy groups in the complexes VIII and X (methyl group protons at 2.10 ppm). The proton integration ratio shows the presence of only two phenyl rings in the complexes which again supports the phenyltin cleavage. The spectrum of compound VI shows phenyltin cleavage as well as the absence of acetoxy group in this compound. However, the spectrum of compound VII shows only the absence of acetoxy group and no loss of phenyl group.

In the case of all these compounds phenyl group protons appear around 7.16-7.33 ppm and azomethine proton at 7.06-7.16 ppm which is shifted down-

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT IR FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF PHENYL TIN(IV) COMPLEXES OF FERROCENYL HYDRAZONES IN NUJOL MULL

Sl. No.	Compound	-C=N-N=C-	C-O	Sn-C	Sn-O	Sn-N	Sn-phenyl
1.	VI	1610 (s)	1240 (s)	610 (m)	560 (m)	370 (s)	1075 (s)
2.	VII	1610 (s)	1245 (s)	610 (m)	560 (m)	340 (s)	1070 (m)
3.	VIII	1600 (s)	1240 (s)	610 (w)	580 (s)	335 (m)	1075 (m)
4.	IX	1600 (w)	1240 (m)	610 (m)	555 (m)	360 (m)	1075 (m)
5.	X	1615 (s)	1260 (s)	615 (s)	560 (m)	380 (s)	1080 (m)

TABLE 3—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFTS (δ) OF COMPLEXES DERIVED FROM TRIPHENYL TIN ACETATE

Sl. No.	Compound	Ferrocenyl group		Azomethine proton	Aromatic	Phenyl group	OCCH ₃ protons
		Unsubstituted C_6H_5	Substituted C_6H_5				
1.	VI	3.9	4.33 4.86	*	8.23	7.4	-
2.	VII	3.9	4.4 4.9	7.16	8.23	7.4	-
3.	VIII	3.93	4.4 5.00	*	8.06	7.16	2.06
4.	X	3.91	4.23 4.83	7.06	8.00 8.66	7.33	2.12
5.	Triphenyltin acetate	-	-	-	-	7.43	2.00

* Superimposed by peaks due to aromatic protons.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

(Fc = Ferrocenyl group)

3a

3b

Fig. 3

field by an order of 1.00 ppm. This downfield shift is due to the chelation through azomethine nitrogen atom. Unsubstituted cyclopentadienyl protons appear as singlet at 3.8-4.3 ppm and protons of substituted cyclopentadienyl ring appear at 4.0-4.4 and 4.4-5.23 ppm as broad peaks as expected.

Structure of compounds VI and VII :

Elemental analysis and spectral studies indicate that compound VI may have the six coordinate, octahedral structure as shown in Fig. 1 and compound VII may have 5-coordinate trigonal bipyramidal structure (Fig. 2).

Structure of compounds VIII-X :

Although it is not possible to identify the characteristic acetoxy group absorption bands at 1540-1565 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of compounds VIII, IX and X in Nujol mull, a new band is seen at 1610-1620 cm^{-1} in the spectra of these compounds in chloroform solution. The appearance of this new band is indicative of some structural changes in solution, but still suggesting a non-ester type of acetoxy group¹⁰. Accordingly, structures 3a and 3b (Fig. 3) can be tentatively suggested for these compounds, the solid compounds existing in dimeric form.

The molecular weight determination in chloroform (vapour-pressure osmometric method) shows the molecular weight to be in between the monomer and dimer, which again suggests that in chloroform solution these compounds may dissociate to monomer and an equilibrium between monomer-dimer exists.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.R.P.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for a Research Fellowship.

References

1. W. H. NELSON and D. F. MARTIN, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 67.
2. S. R. PATIL, U. N. KANTAK and D. N. SEN, Communicated to *Inorg. Chim. Acta*.
3. R. G. R. BACON and W. S. LINDSAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1382.
4. K. NAGANO, H. KINOSHITA and A. HIRAKAWA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Tokyo*, 1964, 12, 1198.
5. R. C. POLLER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, 24, 593.
6. K. KAWAKAMI and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1966, 6, 249.
7. T. TANAKA, M. KOMURA, Y. KAWASAKI and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1964, 1, 484.
8. R. A. CUMMINS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1963, 16, 985.
9. R. A. CUMMINS and J. V. EVANS, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, 21, 1016.
10. M. WADA, M. SHINDO and R. OKAWARA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 95.